

Doyen of Actors: Shivaji Ganesan

Swetha S,

Assistant Professor, Department of English,

Dwaraka Doss Goverdhan Doss Vaishnav College,

Arumbakkam, Chennai.

Abstract:

This research paper explores the life and career of Shivaji Ganesan, known as the "Doyen of Actors" and the "Marlon Brando of South Indian Cinema." Born in 1928, Ganesan began his acting career at seven and starred in over 250 films. His unique acting technique, body and vocal fluidity, and exceptional dialogue delivery have inspired generations. The paper also highlights Ganesan's philosophical approach to acting, his contributions to various drama genres, and his prestigious awards.

Keywords: Theatre, Acting approaches, Cinema, observation and body fluidity.

Introduction:

"All the world's a stage,
And all the men and women merely players;
They have their exits and their entrances;
And one man in his time plays many parts,
His act being seven ages."
- ('As you like it')

This world-famous quote explains the world as a stage, every existing human must play their roles, and each one of them will get their chance and time to do their roles. This paper is about a man who performed innumerable parts in his time and his acting career begins at the age of seven. He is called "The Actor of Actors" and "The Marlon Brando of South Indian Cinema" who played a lead role in

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more than 250 films in Tamil Cinema. He is none other than Shivaji Ganesan the pride of Tamil Cinema.

Sivaji, the Tespian:

Vizhuppuram Chinniah Ganesan, was born on October 1st, 1928, Vizhuppuram district, Tamil Nadu. He was born as a third son to the Chinaiya Manrayar and Rajamani Ammaiyar couple. His father was a railway employee and a freedom fighter. When the day Shivaji Ganesan was born his father was arrested by the British police for his Nationalist movements. His family faced a financial crisis right after his birth so he moved to Trichy. He studied at a Christian school. In School, he was engrossed in arts, singing and speaking dialogues in the school plays. At the age of seven, he watched 'Kataboman Koothu' performed by the theatre troupe called "Kambalathaar Koothu" in front of his house. During those times, the children from the audience were chosen to perform the role of the British soldiers. He went to watch this play with his father and eventually got an opportunity to be on a stage as an actor at the age of seven. At the same time, Yadhartham Ponuswampilai's drama troupe named 'Madurai Sri Balagana Sabha' halted in Trichy for performance. Young Ganesan became enamored of acting, that one "Kataboman" drama made him abandon school and away from home to join this drama company. Since he was interested in singing and acting, he got selected by singing the song "Pazhanivel ithu Thanjam" and saying that he was an orphan to Shankarapani, one of the drama troupe members. This troupe moved from Trichy to Dindugul, where he got the proper foundation for acting. For his drama is equal to discipline. His drama company is like a 'Gurukul' where people from different ages come, live there and gain knowledge. In his biography, he stated how they were trained in a drama company. They have to wake up at 7. a.m. First they will practice the vocals and singing. Secondly, the dance and later they would practice their dialogues and rehearse the play. He was trained by his master, Chinna Ponnuswamy Padayachi. He was called a 'bookworm' by his peers. He always carries the drama scripts and reads. It was a hard period for them. Because of poverty, they couldn't get enough food for all. Despite their poverty, these poor

actors had to perform the roles of kings, warriors and wealthy characters. He tolerated everything for his dream and his passion for acting motivated him to do his job.

His first role after the acting training was the role of 'Sita' from the epic Ramayana. Like the Elizabethan period, drama companies didn't give opportunities for women to act. The male roles would be performed by men and the female roles would be performed by young men who are good-looking and fair. He excelled in the role of 'Sita' and was praised by his master right after his first stage performance.

During his acting career, Shivaji acted four characters in the epic Ramayana: 'Sita', 'Soorpanaga', 'Baratha' and 'Indrajith'. He played both the male and female roles and stunned the audience with his exceptional performance. He has the body fluidity to perform a role.

The ability to move freely and coordinate our body movements smoothly and efficiently is a crucial thing for an expressive performance. Effortless movements with control, using the right movement, right muscles, appropriate expressions and excluding unnecessary movements. Body fluidity is a motor learning mechanism. For body fluidity, one must focus on thinking about the role. The cognitive stage is about understanding the character, giving an imaginary life to the character in one's mind. Then the associative stage, where we can practice the role, do or rehearse what we have already imagined. This would help with what one must do and what not to do. Each and every time of the practice, it will help to groom the character and the performance. The last autonomous stage, where one can do a performance automatically.

When an actor prepares for a female role, he becomes quite feminine in real life. Their walk, tonal variation and preferences would be comparatively feminine and it happens unconsciously. They would be so graceful and delicate in real life. There is a psychological impact after a performance. We can't trace feminine grace in Shivaji's real life even after he performs a number of female characters. He stated that he used to perform multiple roles in a single drama performance. So, he knows how to balance the body and his emotions. Not only the body movements, we have changed the voice according to the role. 'Magarakattu' is a type of voice exercise he trained in the drama company as a

part of his stage performance. Shivaji compared voice exercises to the practice of yoga. Each and every breath has to be in our control on stage. With this type of vocal exercise, he can fluctuate his voice appropriate to his character. His ability to deliver unique dialogue was exceptional. His tenor, tone, diction, and manner were all outstanding. Sivaji spoke Tamil on screen in a way that was mellow and lively, in contrast to the majority of performers in today's Tamil cinema. To suggest that he served as a model for many members of my generation in terms of how to pronounce Tamil lines in dramas is not hyperbole. Because Sivaji Ganesan gave the Tamil language fresh life, generations of Tamils learned to value its beauty and strength. He increased many Tamils' affection for their language. He was called 'Simmakuralon', translated as 'The Lion's voice', all because of the vocals exerThus proves his body and vocal fluidity in a performance.

Shivaji's theory of acting is a traditional form of acting. He just observed the things around him and learned to imitate them with his own style.

According to him, the best actor is one who performs the character as well as possible with his own version rather than just imitation. He calls himself a good observer. A performer should be concerned about angles, lighting, positions, stage space, and audience. He should be highly observant, conscious on stage and skilled at sustaining it till the end of the performance. He did not appreciate the actors who indulge themselves in the fictional character and lose themselves to it. He should not perform unconsciously. When he acted in films, he was very aware of the angles and techniques.

"A word does not start as a word – it is an end product which begins as an impulse, stimulated by attitude and behavior which dictates the need for expression."

— Peter Brook, 'The Empty Space'

As Peter Brook suggests, he too believes that words are a product of deep emotions, and they enhance empathy in a conversation. He understands that language as a dynamic tool and reflection of the inner world of a character. His actions will be in sync with his body language. Even if he has no dialogue to speak, his body will speak to the audience. Like the word-to-word translation method, he would act for each and every word with his unique delicate body language. He was the only one

who could perform Tamil dialogue with ferocious expression in those days. Later in the films, many of the dialogues were written for him.

“Dialogue for me is poetry. I have a passion for poetry. And so, there was no problem for me with rendering it effectively.”

- Shivaji

In 'Parashakthi' (1952), his debut film, his court scene dialogue delivery inspired later-generation actors to emulate his style of Tamil dialogue. In 'Veera Pandiya Kattabomman', he portrays the dream role of a Kattabomman king, showcasing his powerful dialogue, body language, and style. For this performance, he won the Best Actor Award at the Afro-Asian film festival in 1960.

'Thirumbipaar, Manohara, 'Thookkuthookki', 'Illara Jyothi', 'Anbu, Rajarani', 'Ethirparathathu', 'Annayin Aana', 'Kuravanji', 'MaruthanaatuVeeran', 'Ambikapathy', 'Kappalottiya Thamizhan', 'Paasamalar', 'Aalayamani', 'Karnan', 'Thiruvilaiyaadal', 'Saraswathi Sabatham', 'Kandan Karunai', 'Thirumaal Perumai', 'Sivantha Mann', 'Gauravam', 'Rajaraja Chozhan', 'Thanga Pathakkam', etc. these are the list of films where he is remembered for his dialogue delivery.

During his stay at Paramakudi, he watched Swamy Iyar's performance of 'Dumbachari'. Swamy Iyar played nine roles, each role with each emotion. In Indian theater, there are nine emotions called 'Navarasas'. He got very inspired by him performing nine different emotions or Rasas. Later, in his film 'Navaratri' (1964), he got the opportunity to act, in which he played nine different characters signifying wonder, fear, compassion, anger, gentleness, revulsion, romantic passion, courage and happiness. In that movie, one of the roles he had to perform was an artist. He performs 'Therukoothu', a type of Indian folk drama, with Savitri. Shivaji is not a practitioner of folk dramas. Yet, he performs as if he has mastered that art. He states that his observing skills helped him to do all kinds of roles. From a young age, he was exposed to many varieties of plays. Sometimes artists from various states come and perform.

Shivaji and his troupe members would watch the play irrespective of the language barriers. It's just an art and the art language is different from human languages. As theater enthusiasts, they can

comprehend and indulge themselves in the art. Not only in 'Navaratri', he played multiple roles in many other movies. For example, 'Uthama Puthiran' and 'Enga Oor Raja', 'Gowravam' in dual roles, and 'Thrishoolam', 'Deiva Magan' and 'Balae Pandiya' as triple roles in a single film.

The stage property or the "props" are the objects used to give a visual picture of a scene in a performance. It has a crucial role in a performance. In theatrical, space is used to elevate the performance, engage the audience and give a realistic impact to a performance. Shivaji can be called the terrific explorer of the theatrical space and stage properties. While he performs, he uses the props as much as he can and gives meaning or life to the property.

Throughout his career, he played in many social and revolutionary dramas, such as 'Pathi Bakthi', 'Kadharin Vetri', 'Parashakthi', 'Lakshmigandhan', 'Veethi', 'Vimala' or 'The Tears of a widow'. He acted in historical dramas such as 'Shivaji Kanda Indhu Rajiyam', 'Kattaboman', and 'Noorjahan'.

He does a lot of dramas in his movies. In "Annaniyin Aanai," he portrays King Ashoka; in "Rajapart Rangadurai," he plays Hamlet; in "Anbu" and "Ratha Thilagam," he plays Othello; and in "Raja-Rani," he portrays Socrates. Existing beauty is enhanced by the meta-theatrical aspects.

In 1946, for the 7th Periyar's Self-respect Conference, C. N. Annadurai, founder of the Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam, wrote a play called 'Shivaji Kanda Indhu Rajiyam'. He got the opportunity to play 'Shivaji' in this play. Periyar was not an art enthusiast. Like Plato, he also dislikes art and believes art corrupts society. Periya watched him perform the play and praised Ganesan's outstanding performance and called him "Sivaji" Ganesan.

Shivaji, was awarded the Dadasaheb Phalke lifetime achievement award in 1997. He received Padma Shri, Padma Bhushan, Kalaimamani, Chevalier in the Order of Arts and Literature, and 'Kalaikkurusil' in Sri Lanka.

Conclusion:

He founded 'Shivaji Nadaga Mandam', a theatre company that performs and donates to charity, he is a School of drama, allowing others to learn from his performances. He is indelible in the world of theatre and the cinema.

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Bibliography:

1. T. S. Narayanaswamy, 'My Autobiography: Shivaji Ganesan', Sivaji Prabhu Charities Trust, 2002.
2. Jeyaraj, D. B. S. "Sivaji Ganesan Was a World-Class Actor". *Daily Mirror*, 31 July 2021.
<https://www.dailymirror.lk/opinion/Sivaji-Ganesan-was-a-World-ckass-Actor/172-217263>.
3. Brook, 'The Empty Space', Macmillan Publishing Company, 1968.
<http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA22771813>
4. Foy, R. (2021, March 26). What is Method Acting? The Lee Strasberg Theatre & Film Institute.
<https://strasberg.edu/about/what-is-method-acting/>

